

Photocorrosion

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Semiconductors are often decomposed by anodic oxidation or cathodic reduction upon illumination when they are in contact with electrolytes. Examples of semiconductor corrosion are described. The mechanisms of photocorrosion for various materials are reviewed. Stabilization of semiconductor surface against photocorrosion has been discussed and the ways to prevent, to suppress, and to minimize photocorrosion are suggested. Modern analytical techniques are useful tools for future photocorrosion research.

I. Electrochemical Principles of Corrosion

A. Corrosion of metals and alloys :

CORROSION is the interaction of a metal or alloy with its non-metallic environment. Since metals and alloys are conductors and are built up of cations and electrons that are more or less easily dissociable, and the environment usually contains ionically conducting species, most corrosion reactions are electrochemical. The stability of metals has been reviewed in detail¹.

B. Corrosion of semiconductors :

Semiconductors are often decomposed by anodic oxidation or cathodic reduction if they are illuminated in contact with electrolytes². The mechanism of these reactions has been analyzed and studied in some detail³. It appears that the anodic decomposition may be described as a weakening of chemical bonds at the surface of a semiconductor due to the presence of holes, that means a deficiency of electrons in bonding orbitals. The cathodic decomposition may be analogously described as caused by the presence of electrons in the surface, occupying non-bonding or antibonding orbitals. As a result, the weakening of the bonding of surface atoms in both cases facilitates the attack by nucleophilic or electrophilic reactants which are always present in the electrolyte.

In recent years, considerable attention had been given to the properties of semiconductors in contact with electrolytic solutions⁴⁻⁶, and theories had been formulated explaining many of the results. There was a critical problem of corrosion encountered with all of the materials tested, particularly the photocorrosion^{2,3}. In some cases the semiconductors corrode spontaneously in the dark (forming mainly a battery), while in most instances corrosion occurs on illumination. Instead of reduced species in the aqueous electrolyte, holes in the n-type semiconductor valence band were found to oxidize the electrode itself. Holes in such an n-type semiconductor are broken bonds, while electrons in a p-type semiconductor represent excess bonds, so that in either case accumulation of the photogenerated carriers at the semiconductor surface can lead

to a rupturing of the lattice. With n-type CdS, for example, the reaction on illumination is

the two electrons can reduce Cd^{2+} at a counter electrode. The coating of elemental S covers the electrode surface in a few minutes and the reaction stops.

Of course, if an electrode would remain stable under illumination, then it could be applied to generate useful chemical products in a solution, while itself only acting as a photocatalyst. Therefore, photoelectrochemical decomposition of water with semiconductors as catalysts has been extensively studied. In 1972, Fujishima and Honda⁷ showed that it is possible to use the semiconductor TiO_2 (rutile) in contact with water to generate both H_2 and O_2 under illumination, and claimed that the material suffered no degradation. This report soon created great enthusiasm in the field of semiconductor-electrolyte interfaces⁸.

We know the corrosion phenomena, we recognize its serious problems, and we have limited knowledge about it. We are actively searching for its solutions.

II. Examples of Semiconductor Corrosion

A. Photocorrosion of TiO_2 :

Even though the TiO_2 photoanodes have been shown by many investigators to be stable, evidence indicates that they actually undergo slow dissolution in acidic solutions^{9,10}. Upon exposure to an 1N H_2SO_4 solution, the TiO_2 electrode turns velvety black in contrast to the unexposed glassy surface of the crystal. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) reveals the presence of square tapered pits on the exposed surfaces of the crystal. This process is not a simple chemical dissolution because of its absence in the dark. Addition of 1.0 M CoSO_4 or 1.0 M $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ to 1N H_2SO_4 suppresses the anodic photodissolution of TiO_2 as evidenced by the absence of apparent changes or weight loss of the photoanode.

Some evidence of photoanodic dissolution of TiO_2 in alkaline solutions (5.0–7.0 M NaOH) at very high light intensities was also observed; a small depression in the electrode surface after about 1 hr of irradiation appeared¹¹.

B. Stability of titanates :

(a) SrTiO_3 electrodes, before and after the passage of electricity in the photolysis of water with 9.5 M NaOH in $\text{H}_2^{18}\text{O}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, were examined by Wrighton *et al.* They concluded that the SrTiO_3 was stable under conditions where the electrolysis of water was photo assisted. This is the first report to show the photolysis of water without any external bias. Ohashi, McCann and Bockris¹² also found it to be stable when they combined n- SrTiO_3 -p-CdTe and n- SrTiO_3 -p-GaP as stable photoelectric cells.

(b) FeTiO_3 , Fe_2TiO_4 and Fe_3TiO_5 : Iron titanate systems have been studied as possible candidates for semiconductor electrodes in PEC cells by Ginley and Baugham¹⁴. These authors observed the electrochemical degradation of the titanates with leaching of iron out of the surface. This poses a serious problem in spite of the reasonable chemical stability of these materials.

(c) BaTiO_3 : Photolysis of water using BaTiO_3 electrodes has been studied by Nasby and Quinn¹⁵. No apparent electrode degradation has been observed for solutions in the pH range 1.1 to 13.6.

C. Acid dissolution of Fe_2O_3 :

The possibility of using Fe_2O_3 as semiconductor electrodes in photoelectrochemical cells has been investigated. Hardee and Bond¹⁶ observed gas evolution with the anodic current which they attribute to the photo assisted oxidation of water to produce O_2 . They found that the potential for the onset of the photocurrent shifts to more negative values with increasing pH of the solution. The Fe_2O_3 films are seen to be stable at open circuit in basic solutions up to 1 M NaOH. On the other hand, acid solutions (pH < 4.5) slowly dissolve the Fe_2O_3 coating¹⁷.

The acid dissolution of Fe_2O_3 seems to be not related to photocorrosion. It may be simply the increasing solubility of Fe_2O_3 in an acidic solution.

But Yeh and Hackerman¹⁸ reported no noticeable corrosion problems with Fe_2O_3 in pH 4.0 acetate buffer to 5.5 M KOH solutions.

D. SnO_2 :

Photo effects at polycrystalline SnO_2 electrodes have been demonstrated by Kim and Laitinen¹⁹. The photo assisted electrolysis of water by uv irradiation of a Sb-doped SnO_2 electrode has been studied by Wrighton²⁰. In acidic or weakly alkaline solutions, small amounts of H_2O_2 are also formed¹².

E. ZnO and Cu_2O :

Gerischer²¹ states that the reduction of ZnO can occur at high cathodic polarization where the surface degenerates. Thermodynamic considerations by Gerscher²¹ also show that the cathodic and anodic

decomposition potentials are close together and both are far inside the band gap of the Cu_2O . This system is therefore very unstable and unsuitable as a photo electrode in a PEC cell.

F. GaP , GaAs , CdTe , CdS , ZnSe and ZnTe :

According to Memming and Schwandt²², irradiation of an n-GaP electrode in alkaline solutions yields electron flow from GaP to the counter electrode, resulting in photoanodic dissolution of GaP according to the reaction

At higher current densities (10 mA/cm²), the following reaction takes place²³

In acidic solutions, these studies have shown that Ga and P are dissolved in the trivalent and pentavalent states, respectively with the consumption of 6 positive holes.

Analytical studies of the photoanodic dissolution of GaAs have been reported²⁴. In alkaline solutions, GaAs dissolution takes place according to the reaction

The photoanodic dissolution of CdS electrodes has been described^{25,26} according to the reactions

Despite of anodic dissolution of CdTe, the combinations of n- TiO_2 and n- SrTiO_3 with p-CdTe and p-GaP have been reported to form separate, stable self-driven PEC cells¹². Ohashi *et al.*²⁶ have investigated ZnTe and CdTe as possible candidates for photo cathodes in PEC cells. Their studies show that CdTe can be used as stable photocathode in a PEC cell consisting of CdTe/NaOH/ TiO_2 but ZnTe is unstable and has unfavourable photo response characteristics.

The photodecomposition of ZnSe illustrates a common property of binary compound semiconductors²⁷. Very stable semiconductors decompose rapidly in an electrolyte solution on illumination. When an electrode of conducting n-type ZnSe and a piece of Pt wire are immersed in an inert aqueous electrolyte solution and the external leads are short-circuited, nothing happens in the dark. However, if the electrode is illuminated, a remarkably efficient reaction starts. The ZnSe has a band gap of 2.7 eV and is normally pale yellow in colour. After a few minutes of irradiation, its surface turns dark red due to the oxidation of Se^{2-} to Se^0 . Analysis of the solution also shows the dissolution of Zn^{2+} ion. Two electrons pass through the external circuit from the ZnSe electrode to the Pt electrode according to the overall reaction

To understand the relation between the conductivity type and the chemical reaction rate, we may consider that in an ionic compound, the conduction band can be associated with the cations and the valence band with the anions. This may be partially

valid for partially ionic compounds such as ZnSe. Based on the relative thermodynamic properties of the ions, there is a tendency towards a symmetric dissolution. A Zn^{2+} ion in the crystal goes into solution, leaving behind two negative charges on a Se^{2-} ion that remains bound to the solid. For electrostatic reasons, the dissolution soon ceases unless the negative charges on the Se^{2-} can move out of the crystal passing through the external circuit. This is difficult in an n-type semiconductor. In order to move charges out of the crystal it must get to the conduction band, because this is where charge moves in an n-type semiconductor. For getting to the conduction band, it requires 2.7 eV excitation energy which cannot be supplied by thermal excitation at room temperature. As a result, there is no decomposition in the dark. On illumination, holes become available. These flow to the surface and so neutralize the negative charges. At the same time the electrons excited by the radiation flow in the opposite direction through the conduction band and into the external circuit to complete the charge balance. The dissolution of ZnSe crystal continues until it is blocked by the coating of a layer of slightly soluble material on its surface. Theoretically, if the ZnSe had been p-type, the charge neutralization required for the dissolution could have been supplied by the flow of thermally excited holes through the valence band. The dark dissolution should take place. No experiment with the p-type ZnSe was reported⁴⁸.

G. WO_3 :

WO_3 shows no weight changes after prolonged passage of electricity under strong irradiation.

H. Si :

Another kind of reaction that consumes the electrode material is the anodic oxidation of covalent semiconductors requiring a supply of holes to the surface⁴⁹. An important example that requires a supply of holes is the anodic oxidation of Si. For an n-type crystal there is a Schottky barrier at its surface with the usual rectifying i-V behaviour. The overall reaction is

the experimentally obtained values for z vary from 2 to 4 depending on the reaction conditions.

III. Stabilization of Semiconductor Surface against Photocorrosion

Recently, impressive progress has been made in the development of photoelectrochemical solar cells. However, a major difficulty remains, that is, the photocorrosion of desirable anode materials such as GaAs and n-Si. Ultimately, the goal is to make photoelectric cells using polycrystalline materials^{37,44}, which will contain different defects. Simple theory suggests that defective areas of the crystal surface will be more difficult to stabilize⁵⁰. Experimentally speaking, it is unclear what effects these defects will have on the photoelectrochemical corrosion processes.

A great number of efforts have been made in the past to prevent, to suppress, or to minimize photocorrosion. These efforts may be summarized as follows.

A. Electrode coating :

The approach to the dissolution problem has been the use of inert coatings on the photoanode surface. Gourgand and Elliott²⁹ have described the use of a MoO_3 coating to prevent the electrolytic corrosion of n-GaAs under irradiation. Nakato *et al*³⁰ have reported the coating of a thin transparent gold film to the n-GaP surface.

Coating or deposition of a wide band-gap stable semiconductor on the surface of the unstable semiconductor has been attempted in an effort to reduce the extent of anodic photodecomposition. Tomkiewicz *et al*³¹ describe the sputtering of TiO_2 , SnO_2 , Nb_2O_5 , Al_2O_3 and Si_3N_4 on GaAs and GaAlAs. Single crystalline semiconductors, such as n-Si, p-Si, n-GaAs, p-GaAs, n-GaP, n-InP and n-CdS have been coated with n- TiO_2 , resulting in unfavourable results³². However, Bockris and Uosaki³³ have reported the chemical vapour deposition of TiO_2 on CdS single crystals. The efficiency of this electrode is reported to be four times greater than a TiO_2 single crystal in contrast to the results of Kohl *et al*³⁴. Ghosh and Maruska³⁴ have reported the reduced photocorrosion by the use of TiO_2 film on CdSe.

In the investigation of electrocatalysis or inhibition of electrode processes of a reactant (R) at the metal electrode (M) in the presence of surface layer (S), Schultze and Habib³⁵ conclude that electrocatalysis and inhibition by electrosorbates and protective layers is a three-parameter problem. It depends on (a) the type of layer (ionic, covalent, neutral oxide, salt), (b) the type of reaction, and (c) the type of influence (chemical, electrostatic, geometric, etc.).

Electrodes covered with thin permeable polymer films have been studied by Doblhofer³⁶. The films prepared on the anode of the glow discharge act as semi-permeable membranes. Hydrogen can be oxidized on the Pt-polymer interface of these polymer covered electrodes at rates comparable to uncovered Pt, while the films were impermeable to iron ions.

B. Use of redox system :

The stability problems associated with the use of CdX ($X=S, Se, Te$) and GaY ($Y=P, As$) as photoanodes in PEC cells have led some investigators to suppress anodic dissolution by the use of suitable redox systems in the electrolyte. Fe(II)-EDTA is a good stabilizing agent at pH 3 for n-GaAs³⁸.

The use of wide-gap semiconductors in PEC systems is hampered by the fact that these electrodes utilize only a small portion of the solar spectrum for efficient energy conversion. The dye sensitization approach restricts light absorption to the order of 1-2% since only monolayers of dyes are active

for electron transfer. Therefore, efforts should be made on the achievement of good stability with low band gap semiconductors like GaP, GaAs, etc. by incorporation of suitable redox couples in the electrolyte¹⁷. The stability of common semiconductors used as photoanodes with values of their band gap, flatbands and quantum efficiency is listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY OF SEMICONDUCTOR ELECTRODES FOR PHOTOCATALYTIC DECOMPOSITION OF WATER*

Material	E_{BG} eV	E_{FB} eV	Highest quantum efficiency %	Stability
TiO ₂	3.0	0.05	100	Stable
SrTiO ₃	3.2	-0.2	100	Stable
BaTiO ₃	3.3	0.1	30	Stable
KTaO ₃	3.5	-0.2	6	Stable
FeTO ₃	2.2	1.1	15	Leaching of Fe noted
Fe ₂ TiO ₅	2.2	1.2	15	Leaching of Fe noted
Fe ₂ TiO ₄	2.2	1.5	15	Stable
Fe ₃ O ₄	2.2	0.7	40	Stable at pH > 4.5
Cu ₂ O	2.2	-	-	Corrodes
CuO	1.7	1.0	-	Corrodes
WO ₃	2.7	0.5	100	Stable in acid
ZnO	3.2	0	-	Corrodes
SnO ₂	3.5	0.5	100	Stable
SiC	3.0	-1.3	-	Corrodes
V ₂ O ₅	2.75	1.2	-	Corrodes
Si	1.1	-0.7	-	Corrodes
InP	1.3	-0.2	-	Corrodes
GaAs	1.4	-0.5	-	Corrodes
GaP	2.2	-1.0	-	p-type stable
CdS	2.4	-0.5	-	Corrodes
CdSe	1.7	-0.2	-	Corrodes
ZrO ₂	5.0	-1.0	-	Stable
Cr ₂ O ₃	1.4	-	-	Corrodes, poor response
CoO	0.5	0.8	-	Corrodes, poor response

* Abstracted from Table 1 in Ref. 9.

C. Non-aqueous solvent system :

The corrosion problems exhibited by so many of the small band gap semiconductors will be relieved in a non-aqueous electrolyte. For example, Kohl and Bard⁸⁷ report the photocorrosion of the semiconductors (n- and p-GaAs) electrodes in acetonitrile solutions is suppressed and does not occur until potentials were well positive of the flat band potential.

IV. Future Research of Photocorrosion

In the photoelectrochemistry, there are two challenging problems facing us, namely, (i) efficient and readily available electrode materials⁸⁸ and (ii) photocorrosion. For the long range research on photocorrosion the following recommendations may be suggested.

A. For better theoretical understanding of the photocorrosion of materials, particularly semiconductors, to study the electrode surfaces with modern surface techniques^{88,89}.

(a) Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) has, since its inception as a commercially available surface chemical analytical technique, enjoyed a strong interaction with the field of material science. Corrosion is primarily concerned with

the interaction of materials with their environments. AES is sensitive to all elements except H and He, and the relative sensitivities for most elements varies by only about one order of magnitude. Each element has relatively few strong Auger peaks, which limits peak overlap, and most elements do not show strong peak energy shifts, making elemental identification easy.

(b) X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, ESCA) offers the researcher a unique capability for detecting chemical species in thin (1-2 nm) surface films, with only minor perturbation from the exciting radiation. This technique is important for the identification of corrosion imitators and for determining the nature of the first films formed in corrosion process. XPS is useful for (i) oxide-metal differentiation, (ii) differentiation of oxidation states, and (iii) identifying other chemical changes. It can provide more structural information as more is learned about its spectra of corrosion elements. The use of synergistic analytical technique such as scanning Auger microscopy, secondary ion mass spectroscopy, and ion micro probe, will provide some measure of spatial definition when combined with XPS.

B. To continue the current efforts to find ways to stabilize the electrodes such as coatings, doping, and combinations of electrodes^{40,41}. It seems that the glow discharge polymer coating deserves more research efforts⁸⁶.

C. To stabilize the electrode surfaces with ion implantation. The ion implantation in semiconductors has been known for sometime⁴²; however, little is known about its study in photocorrosion

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Gas Research Institute and the Research Administration, University of Missouri-Kansas City.

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